

APPLICATION OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN FORMING THE COMPETENCE OF FUTURE TEACHERS

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Annotation: This article is devoted to the study of the role of media educational technologies and aspects of their use in the system of developing the information competence of future teachers in the process of their professional training in higher education.

Key words: information competence, information technologies, information society, media education, media educational technologies.

Introduction. At this historical stage of its development, modern society is distinguished by its informational nature, since the main products of human production today are knowledge and information. In the system of development of the information society, the role of media resources for the life of representatives of modern society is increasing. The development of the information society is characterized by the emergence of numerous information and communication technologies, including media technologies [2, 3].

Considering the role of modern information resources in the process of forming the personality of representatives of the domestic society at this stage of its development, the state and society require specialists with the ability to understand the latest information technologies, the ability to select objectively useful and reliable information, and use it to effectively transform the surrounding reality [1, 4].

Future teachers are responsible for shaping the new generation. In this regard, in the system of professional training of future teachers during their training in

higher education, given that the leading conceptual basis of professional education today is the competency-based approach, one of the main tasks is the formation of information competence of future specialists [3, 6, 7].

The process of forming the professional competence of a future specialist is impossible without knowledge of its structure, and therefore let us turn to the consideration of the components of information competence [5, 8, 9]. The researchers identified the following components of the competence analyzed in this study:

- obtaining information - the user selects information rationally and effectively;
- evaluation of information - the user evaluates information critically and competently;
- use of information - the user uses information accurately and creatively [2, 10].

The process of developing the information competence of future specialists in the field of education also has a certain structure. Following researchers E.V. Shevchuk and N.S. Kolyeva, we will highlight motivational, content-based, procedural and reflective components as structural components of the process of forming information for future teachers [5, 11, 12].

Having examined the essence of the concept of “information competence,” let us turn to studying the role of media educational technologies in the system of its formation among future teachers in the process of their professional training in higher education.

With the development of the information society and new information and technical means of teaching in the education system, prerequisites have emerged for the development and establishment of a new direction - media pedagogy, based on media educational technologies.

According to the definition given in the Uzbek Pedagogical Encyclopedia, media education is “a direction in pedagogy that advocates for schoolchildren to study the laws of mass communication (press, television, radio, cinema, video). The main tasks of media education are to prepare the new generation for life in modern

information conditions, for the perception of any information, to teach a person to understand it, to be aware of the consequences of its impact on the psyche, to master methods of communication based on non-verbal forms of communication using technical means” [7, 13, 14] .

Researchers define media education as “the process of personal development with the help and on the material of mass communication (media) with the aim of creating a culture of communication with the media, creative, communication abilities, critical thinking, skills of full perception, interpretation, analysis and evaluation of media texts, teaching various forms of self-expression using media technology" [1, 15, 16].

Thus, in this study, based on the above, the term “media education” will be understood as part of the educational process aimed at creating a media culture in society, preparing an individual for safe and effective interaction with the modern mass media system, including traditional ones (print media, radio, cinema, television), and the latest (communication via computer, Internet, mobile telephony) media, taking into account the development of information and communication technologies [21].

Researchers understand the term “information competence” as “possession of effective ways of working with information that has different meaningful meanings and different forms of presentation, the ability to assess the quality and reliability of information coming from various sources, readiness for successful information interaction with other people” [17, 18, 19].

Based on the results of the analysis of pedagogical research on aspects of the formation of information competence and the problems of media pedagogy, we conclude that among the most important factors shaping the personal, information and professional competence of a teacher is the inclusion of media education and its technologies in the system of professional training of future teachers [20, 22].

In domestic science, the problems of media education and the use of elements of media educational technologies in the educational process of higher education are

reflected in the works of such researchers as A.V. Fedorov, A.V. Sharikov, N.P. Ryzhikh, I.M. Khizhnyak, T. V. Stroganova. Based on the study of the works of these scientists, we can assert that in modern pedagogical science, media educational technologies are considered in the meaning of means of organizing activities using media to achieve pedagogical goals.

Based on the understanding of the concept of technology in the sense of a set of methods and tools necessary to achieve the desired result, a method of transforming what is given into what is necessary, let us clarify that this concept is one of the fundamental ones in the methodology of media education, since the use of any technology has a great influence on the result of education.

Media educational technologies of education at the present stage of their development include not only traditional media, such as periodicals, radio, television, but also the latest information technologies, including software and hardware devices operating on the basis of computer technology, information exchange systems that ensure the implementation of operations on the collection, accumulation, storage, processing and transmission of information.

Within the framework of media pedagogy, its component branch is also distinguished - media didactics. The list of its functions includes:

- development of the theory of media education and training;
- scientific substantiation of the content of media education, study of patterns, principles, methods and organizational forms of training with the involvement of media products;
- implementation of the principles of humanization of education;
- assistance in raising the intellectual, cultural, spiritual, moral level of the future specialist.

The effectiveness of the use of media educational technologies in the system of forming the components of information competence of future teachers in the process of their professional training in higher education is justified by the functions

that they perform. So, media educational technologies in the system of training a future teacher are aimed at:

- informatization of the educational process, which is implemented in ensuring the availability of various sources of information;
- activation of educational and cognitive activities of students;
- increasing students' motivation to learn;
- interactive learning;
- monitoring of the educational process;
- increasing the efficiency of students' assimilation of educational material;
- encouragement for creative activity by preparing presentations using computer programs;
- attracting students to participate in video conferences and working with foreign students.

To effectively implement the process of forming the components of a future teacher's information competence using media educational technologies, teachers must have a number of skills:

- use information technology to demonstrate printed or graphic documents, audio and video materials;
- create presentations;
- systematize and process information using tables, technological maps;
- build comparative graphs and tables, identify patterns using a computer;
- apply information technologies to model processes and objects;
- create drawings and sketches;
- use computer testing;
- be able to use the capabilities of the Internet to solve various pedagogical issues, in order to collect information, to participate in Internet conferences, to gain access to scientific, pedagogical and methodological data.

Conclusions. Thus, the formation of information competence of future teachers in the process of their professional training in higher education is an urgent

pedagogical problem that requires the development of methodological solutions. One of the effective means of developing information competence is media educational technologies, the use of which in the system of professional training of specialists makes it possible to form the main components of information culture and literacy of future teachers.

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